

Supplementary Material

For the Manuscript: “Strategic Data Center Load Shifting: Implications for Market Efficiency and Transmission Value”

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Proof of Proposition 1

Proposition 1. *Without loss of generality, consider a positive load shift $\delta > 0$ from A to B. Let p_{g_A} and p_{g_B} denote the pre-shift dispatch levels of the marginal generators g_A and g_B , respectively. We assume $p_{g_A} \neq P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}$ so that exactly one marginal generator changes first as δ increases. Two cases then arise, depending on which zone’s marginal generator changes first.*

Case 1. *(Marginal generator at B changes first). Suppose*

$$P_{g_B} - p_{g_B} < p_{g_A}.$$

Let $\tau_1 := P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}$ be the threshold where generator g_B reaches capacity. Then, for $\delta \leq \tau_1$:

$$\Delta G(\delta) = \begin{cases} \Delta P(\delta), & \delta \in [0, \tau_1), \\ \Delta P(\delta) - \kappa_1, & \delta = \tau_1, \end{cases}$$

where the discontinuity κ_1 is given by

$$\kappa_1 := (C_{g_{B+1}} - C_{g_B})(x_B + \tau_1) > 0.$$

Case 2. *(Marginal generator at A changes first). Suppose*

$$p_{g_A} < P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}.$$

Let $\tau_2 := p_{g_A}$ be the threshold where generator g_A is fully de-committed. Then, for $\delta \leq \tau_2$:

$$\Delta G(\delta) = \begin{cases} \Delta P(\delta), & \delta \in [0, \tau_2), \\ \Delta P(\delta) + \kappa_2, & \delta = \tau_2, \end{cases}$$

where the discontinuity κ_2 is given by

$$\kappa_2 := (C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau_2) > 0.$$

Proof. Since A and B are independent (with $F = 0$), each zone’s economic dispatch problem can be solved separately. In each zone, generators are dispatched in increasing order of marginal cost until demand is met. For a shift δ , zone A serves $x_A - \delta$ and zone B serves $x_B + \delta$.

As long as the marginal generators remain the same, dispatch in each zone changes only through a one-for-one adjustment of their marginal unit. Thus,

$$\Delta G(\delta) = (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})\delta = (\lambda_B(\delta) - \lambda_A(\delta))\delta = \Delta P(\delta),$$

so system and consumer objectives are aligned for sufficiently small δ .

We now examine the basis-change points at which a marginal generator switches.

Case 1: Generator at B hits capacity first. At $\delta = \tau_1 := P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}$, generator g_B becomes fully dispatched and g_{B+1} becomes marginal. Thus,

$$\lambda_B(\tau_1) = C_{g_{B+1}}.$$

The change in system generation cost is given by:

$$\Delta G(\tau_1) = (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})\tau_1.$$

while the flexible consumer cost changes by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P(\tau_1) &= C_{g_A}(x_A - \tau_1) + C_{g_{B+1}}(x_B + \tau_1) - (C_{g_A}x_A + C_{g_B}x_B) \\ &= \Delta G(\tau_1) + (C_{g_{B+1}} - C_{g_B})(x_B + \tau_1). \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging gives the stated discontinuity:

$$\Delta G(\tau_1) = \Delta P(\tau_1) - \kappa_1.$$

Case 2: Generator at A fully de-commits first. At $\delta = \tau_2 := p_{g_A}$, generator g_A de-commits and g_{A-1} becomes marginal, so

$$\lambda_A(\tau_2) = C_{g_{A-1}}.$$

The change in system generation cost is given by:

$$\Delta G(\tau_2) = (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})\tau_2,$$

while the flexible consumer cost changes by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P(\tau_2) &= C_{g_{A-1}}(x_A - \tau_2) + C_{g_B}(x_B + \tau_2) - (C_{g_A}x_A + C_{g_B}x_B) \\ &= \Delta G(\tau_2) - (C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau_2). \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging yields:

$$\Delta G(\tau_2) = \Delta P(\tau_2) + \kappa_2.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1

Theorem 1 (Externalities at basis changes). *Without loss of generality, consider a positive load shift $\delta = \tau > 0$ from A to B that is exactly the minimal shift required to change the optimal basis of the market clearing problem (i.e., to induce a change in the marginal generator at either A or B). Let p_{g_A} and p_{g_B} denote the pre-shift dispatch levels of the marginal generators at A and B .*

The system and consumer objectives are misaligned with respect to δ if and only if all of the following conditions hold:

- (i) *The minimal basis-changing shift causes de-commitment of the marginal generator at A :*

$$\tau = p_{g_A} < P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}.$$

- (ii) *Before the shift, the marginal generator at B is strictly more expensive:*

$$C_{g_B} > C_{g_A}.$$

- (iii) *The downward jump in the price at A (from switching g_A to g_{A-1}) offsets the increase in price exposure at B :*

$$(C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau) > (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})\tau.$$

Proof. Let us consider two cases depending on which marginal generator changes first.

Case 1: Generator at B hits capacity first. From Proposition 1, we have

$$\Delta G(\delta) = \begin{cases} \Delta P(\delta), & \delta \in [0, \tau_1), \\ \Delta P(\delta) - \kappa_1, & \delta = \tau_1, \end{cases}$$

with $\kappa_1 > 0$. Hence

$$\Delta G(\delta) \leq \Delta P(\delta) \quad \forall \delta \in [0, \tau_1],$$

with strict inequality at $\delta = \tau_1$. In particular, for the basis-change shift $\delta = \tau_1$,

$$\Delta P(\tau_1) < 0 \implies \Delta G(\tau_1) < 0.$$

Thus, any load shift that reduces the flexible consumer cost also reduces system cost; there is no misalignment at $\delta = \tau_1$. Therefore, misalignment at the minimal basis-changing shift cannot occur in Case 1, and must occur (if at all) in Case 2, i.e., when $\tau = \tau_2 = p_{g_A} < P_{g_B} - p_{g_B}$.

Case 2: Generator at A fully decommits first. Note that this case corresponds to satisfying condition (i). From Proposition 1, for $\delta < \tau_2$,

$$\Delta G(\delta) = \Delta P(\delta),$$

and at the basis-change shift $\delta = \tau_2$,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta G(\tau_2) &= (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}) \tau_2, \\ \Delta P(\tau_2) &= (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}) \tau_2 - (C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau_2).\end{aligned}$$

A flexible consumer is incentivized to choose $\delta = \tau_2$ if and only if this shift reduces their procurement cost:

$$\Delta P(\tau_2) < 0 \iff (C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau_2) > (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}) \tau_2,$$

which corresponds to condition (iii). Likewise, shifting increases system generation cost if and only if

$$\Delta G(\tau_2) > 0 \iff C_{g_B} > C_{g_A},$$

which corresponds to condition (ii).

Combining the two, strategic misalignment at the basis-change shift occurs exactly when shifting by $\delta = \tau_2$ is privately beneficial yet socially costly:

$$\Delta P(\tau_2) < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta G(\tau_2) > 0 \iff \begin{cases} C_{g_B} > C_{g_A}, \\ (C_{g_A} - C_{g_{A-1}})(x_A - \tau_2) > (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}) \tau_2. \end{cases}$$

This is precisely the set of conditions stated in the theorem. \square

Proof of Theorem 2

Theorem 2 (Zero bilevel marginal value of transmission). *Fix initial transmission capacity $F_0 \geq 0$ and let $\delta_0 := \delta^*(F_0)$ be the consumer-optimal load shift. Suppose the following conditions hold:*

(A1) *Marginal generation costs satisfy $C_{g_A} < C_{g_{A+1}} < C_{g_B}$ and the transmission line is congested from A to B:*

$$\lambda_A = C_{g_A} < C_{g_B} = \lambda_B, \quad f = F_0.$$

(A2) *Strategic positioning is profitable:*

$$(C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(x_A - \delta_0) > (C_{g_B} - C_{g_{A+1}}) \delta_0,$$

so that g_A is being dispatched at level $p_{g_A} = P_{g_A}$.

(A3) *The marginal generator g_B has downward headroom: $p_{g_B} > 0$.*

Define the threshold transmission capacity:

$$\Gamma := \left(\frac{C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A}}{C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}} \right) x_A - \delta_0$$

and the upper limit:

$$F_1 := F_0 + \min \{ \Gamma, \bar{\delta} - \delta_0 \}$$

Then for all $F \in [F_0, F_1]$:

(i) The transmission constraint remains binding with positive shadow price:

$$\mu^+ = C_{g_B} - C_{g_A} > 0.$$

(ii) The marginal value of transmission w.r.t. the system objective is zero under load shifting:

$$-\frac{d}{dF} G(\delta^*(F), F) = 0.$$

(iii) The marginal value of transmission w.r.t. the flexible consumer objective is negative under load shifting:

$$-\frac{d}{dF} P(\delta^*(F), F) = C_{g_A} - C_{g_B} < 0.$$

Proof. Let us first express the stationarity, complementary slackness, and dual feasibility conditions for the economic dispatch problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_g} &= C_g - \lambda_i + \eta_g^+ - \eta_g^- = 0, & g \in \mathcal{G}_i, i \in \{A, B\} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial f} &= \lambda_A - \lambda_B + \mu^+ - \mu^- = 0 \\ \mu^+(f - F) &= 0, \mu^-(-f - F) = 0 \\ \eta_g^+(p_g - P_g) &= 0, \eta_g^-(-p_g) = 0, & g \in \mathcal{G}_A \cup \mathcal{G}_B \\ \mu^+, \mu^-, \eta^+, \eta^- &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Together with primal feasibility, these provide sufficient conditions for optimality of the economic dispatch problem. By assumption, the optimality conditions for the economic dispatch problem with δ_0, F_0 are satisfied by:

$$p_{g_A} = P_{g_A} \implies \lambda_A = C_{g_A}, \eta_{g_A}^+ = \eta_{g_A}^- = 0 \quad (2a)$$

$$p_{g_B} > 0 \implies \lambda_B = C_{g_B}, \eta_{g_B}^+ = \eta_{g_B}^- = 0 \quad (2b)$$

$$f = F_0 \implies \mu^+ = \lambda_B - \lambda_A, \mu^- = 0, \quad (2c)$$

$$p_g = P_g \implies \eta_g^+ = C_{g_A} - C_g, \eta_g^- = 0, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}_A, g < g_A \quad (2d)$$

$$p_g = 0 \implies \eta_g^+ = 0, \eta_g^- = C_g - C_{g_A}, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}_A, g > g_A \quad (2e)$$

$$p_g = P_g \implies \eta_g^+ = C_{g_B} - C_g, \eta_g^- = 0, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}_B, g < g_B \quad (2f)$$

$$p_g = 0 \implies \eta_g^+ = 0, \eta_g^- = C_g - C_{g_B}, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}_B, g > g_B \quad (2g)$$

Because the economic dispatch problem is a linear program, optimal dual variables (and hence LMPs at degenerate operating points) may be non-unique. In particular, when $p_{g_A} = P_{g_A}$, the LMP at zone A may lie in the interval $[C_{g_A}, C_{g_{A+1}}]$. We therefore adopt a tie-breaking convention and select the economically relevant dual as the limit of a vanishing perturbation in the direction of decreased load shifting, i.e., $\lambda_A = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow \delta_0^+} \lambda_A(\delta, F_0) = C_{g_A}$.

This choice provides a valid dual solution for the unperturbed problem and is without loss of generality.

Let p'_g and f' denote the optimal dispatch decision for generator g and transmission flow respectively as functions of the load shift δ and transmission capacity F . Additionally, let $\varepsilon > 0$ be an infinitesimal increase in transmission capacity and, fixing δ_0 , consider a solution given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
p'_{g_{A+1}}(\delta_0, F_0 + \varepsilon) = \varepsilon &\implies \lambda_A = C_{g_{A+1}}, \eta_{g_{A+1}}^+ = \eta_{g_{A+1}}^- = 0 \\
p'_{g_B}(\delta_0, F_0 + \varepsilon) = p_{g_B} - \varepsilon &\implies \lambda_B = C_{g_B}, \eta_{g_B}^+ = \eta_{g_B}^- = 0 \\
f = F_0 + \varepsilon &\implies \mu^+ = \lambda_B - \lambda_A, \mu^- = 0, \\
p_g = P_g &\implies \eta_g^+ = C_{g_{A+1}} - C_g, \eta_g^- = 0, & g \in \mathcal{G}_A, g < g_{A+1} \\
p_g = 0 &\implies \eta_g^+ = 0, \eta_g^- = C_g - C_{g_{A+1}}, & g \in \mathcal{G}_A, g > g_{A+1} \\
p_g = P_g &\implies \eta_g^+ = C_{g_B} - C_g, \eta_g^- = 0, & g \in \mathcal{G}_B, g < g_B \\
p_g = 0 &\implies \eta_g^+ = 0, \eta_g^- = C_g - C_{g_B}, & g \in \mathcal{G}_B, g > g_B
\end{aligned}$$

Note that this solution satisfies primal feasibility as well as the stationarity, dual feasibility, and complementary slackness conditions given in (1). Consequently, this solution is optimal for the economic dispatch problem with $(\delta_0, F_0 + \varepsilon)$.

Increasing F by ε allows the system operator to reduce expensive dispatch at B by ε and increase dispatch at A by ε . Since g_A is already at capacity, the next-cheapest unit g_{A+1} enters the margin and the flexible consumer's cost increases by:

$$P(\delta_0, F_0 + \varepsilon) - P(\delta_0, F_0) = (C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(x_A - \delta_0).$$

Because g_{A+1} raises the price at A , the flexible consumer strictly prefers to restore g_A as the marginal generator. This is achieved by increasing the load shift by exactly the same amount:

$$\delta^*(F_0 + \varepsilon) = \delta_0 + \varepsilon.$$

Doing so reverts the solution to the pre-expansion dispatch for all variables (2) except the flow:

$$f(\delta^*(F_0 + \varepsilon), F_0 + \varepsilon) = F_0 + \varepsilon.$$

Because the redispatch is exactly reversed, the price difference remains unchanged:

$$\mu^+(\delta^*(F), F) = \lambda_B - \lambda_A = C_{g_B} - C_{g_A} > 0.$$

Consequently, the shadow price of the transmission capacity constraint remains equal to the price difference:

$$\mu^+(\delta^*(F_0 + \varepsilon), F_0 + \varepsilon) = \lambda_B - \lambda_A = C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}.$$

while the marginal value of transmission to the system is zero:

$$-\frac{d}{dF} G(\delta^*(F), F) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} -\frac{G(\delta^*(F_0 + \varepsilon), F_0 + \varepsilon) - G(\delta_0, F_0)}{\varepsilon} = 0$$

and the marginal value of transmission to the consumer is negative:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d}{dF}P(\delta^*(F), F) &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} -\frac{P(\delta^*(F_0 + \varepsilon), F_0 + \varepsilon) - P(\delta_0, F_0)}{\varepsilon} \\ &= -\frac{(C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})\varepsilon}{\varepsilon} = C_{g_A} - C_{g_B} < 0. \end{aligned}$$

The consumer can continue offsetting transmission expansions so long as:

1. It does not violate the flexibility limit:

$$\delta_0 + (F - F_0) \leq \bar{\delta}.$$

2. Strategic positioning at the upper capacity limit of g_A remains profitable:

$$\begin{aligned} (C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(x_A - (\delta_0 + (F - F_0))) &> (C_{g_B} - C_{g_{A+1}})(\delta_0 + (F - F_0)) \\ (C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(x_A - \delta_0) - (C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(F - F_0) &> (C_{g_B} - C_{g_{A+1}})\delta_0 + (C_{g_B} - C_{g_{A+1}})(F - F_0) \\ (C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A})(x_A - \delta_0) - (C_{g_B} - C_{g_{A+1}})\delta_0 &> (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})(F - F_0) \\ C_{g_{A+1}}x_A - C_{g_A}x_A + C_{g_A}\delta_0 - C_{g_B}\delta_0 &> (C_{g_B} - C_{g_A})(F - F_0) \\ \left(\frac{C_{g_{A+1}} - C_{g_A}}{C_{g_B} - C_{g_A}}\right)x_A - \delta_0 &> (F - F_0). \end{aligned}$$

Together these give $F < F_1$, completing the proof. □